

Effect of natalizumab on oxidative damage biomarkers in relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis

Inmaculada Tasset^{1,*}, Carmen Bahamonde^{2,*}, Eduardo Agüera²,
Cristina Conde², Antonio H. Cruz⁵, Aleyda Pérez-Herrera^{3,4},
Félix Gascón⁵, Ana I. Giraldo¹, María C. Ruiz¹, Rafael Lillo⁶,
Fernando Sánchez-López², Isaac Túnez¹

¹Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Faculty of Medicine/Maimonides Institute for Research in Biomedicine of Cordoba (IMIBIC)/Reina Sofia University Hospital/University of Cordoba, Spain

²Department of Neurology, IMIBIC/Reina Sofia University Hospital/University of Cordoba, Spain

³Lipids and Atherosclerosis Research Unit, IMIBIC/Reina Sofia University Hospital/University of Cordoba, Spain

⁴The Spanish Biomedical Research Centre in Physiopathology of Obesity and Nutrition (CIBERObn), Carlos III Health Institute (ISCIII), Spain

⁵Department of Clinical Analysis, IMIBIC/Regional Hospital of Pedroches Valley/University of Cordoba, Spain

⁶Department of Sociosanitary, Radiology and Physical Medicine, Psychiatry, Section, Faculty of Medicine, University of Cordoba, Spain

Correspondence: Isaac Túnez, e-mail: fm2tufii@uco.es

Abstract:

Background: Natalizumab is a monoclonal antibody used to treat multiple sclerosis. This study sought to determine whether the protective action of natalizumab involved a reduction in oxidative damage.

Methods: Twenty-two multiple sclerosis patients fulfilling the revised McDonald criteria were assigned to treatment with 300 mg natalizumab intravenously once monthly (infusion every 4 weeks) in accordance with Spanish guidelines. Carbonylated proteins, 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine, total glutathione, reduced glutathione, superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase, and myeloperoxidase levels were measured at baseline and after 14 months' treatment, and the antioxidant gap was calculated.

Results: Natalizumab prompted a drop in oxidative-damage biomarker levels, together with a reduction both in myeloperoxidase levels and in the myeloperoxidase/neutrophil granulocyte ratio. Interestingly, natalizumab induced nuclear translocation of Nrf2 and a fall in serum vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 levels.

Conclusion: These findings suggest that natalizumab has a beneficial effect on oxidative damage found in MS patients.

Key words:

adhesion molecules, multiple sclerosis, natalizumab, Nrf2, oxidative stress

* Equal contribution

Abbreviations: BBB – blood-brain barrier, CNS – central nervous system, EDSS – Expanded Disability Status Scale, GAP – antioxidant gap, GPx – glutathione peroxidase, GSH – reduced glutathione, MPO – myeloperoxidase, NF- κ B – nuclear factor- κ B, Nrf2 – nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2, 8-OHdG – 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine, PAO – total antioxidant capacity, RNS – reactive nitrogen species, ROS – reactive oxygen species, RR-MS – relapsing-remitting-multiple sclerosis, sICAM-1 – serum inter-cellular adhesion molecule 1, SOD – superoxide dismutase, sVCAM – serum vascular cell adhesion molecule-1

Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) the most common cause of non-traumatic disability in young adults is a chronic neuroinflammatory autoimmune disease of the central nervous system (CNS) which begins with acute inflammatory demyelination and axonal injury. Although its etiology remains unclear, both environmental factors and genetic susceptibility appear to play some role. Its pathogenesis is known to include the passage of leukocytes across the blood-brain barrier (BBB) [10].

A number of studies report that reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a major role in myelin phagocytosis, contributing to several of the processes underlying MS pathogenesis [9, 19, 20, 32, 38]. The inflammatory response gives rise to the production of both ROS and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) through monocyte interactions with brain endothelium; ROS production induces cytoskeletal rearrangements, loss of BBB integrity, tight-junction alterations and the extravasation of leukocytes into the central nervous system (CNS) [6, 38, 39].

Natalizumab (Tysabri, Biogen Idec, Inc. and Elan Pharmaceuticals, Inc.) is a monoclonal antibody directed against the α -4 subunit of the α -4/ β -1 heterodimeric VLA-4 molecule, which is constitutively expressed on mononuclear immune cells. α -4- β -1-Integrin plays a major role in the transmigration of immune cells across the BBB [3, 35]. Recent research has shown that this treatment reduces both lesion formation [27] and axonal damage [11] in relapsing-remitting-multiple sclerosis (RR-MS).

The present study, therefore, sought to determine whether other markers of oxidative damage and antioxidant systems in RR-MS patients are affected by natalizumab therapy, with a view to better understanding the pathophysiology of the disease, and the mechanisms through which natalizumab treatment achieves its effects.

Materials and Methods

Patients and sample collection

Once informed consent had been obtained, 24 RR-MS patients from the Department of Neurology at the Reina Sofía University Hospital in Córdoba (Spain) were enrolled in the study. Patient clinical data are shown in Table 1. Patients, all of whom fulfilled revised McDonald criteria [25], were assigned to treatment with 300 mg natalizumab (anti-VLA-4; Tysabri, Biogen Idec, Cambridge, MA, USA) administered intravenously once a month (infusion every 4 weeks) in accordance with current Spanish guidelines. Medical history and additional clinical data such as relapse count during the study period were recorded prospectively in the hospital registry. Clinical examination using the Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) [16] was performed by a trained neurologist. Blood samples were taken from the antecubital vein immediately prior to the first natalizumab infusion (baseline) and before the 14th infusion (56 weeks, approx. 14 months; MS-14), as shown in Figure 1. Blood was collected from antecubital vein between 16:00 and 17:30 p.m. Samples were placed in chilled Vacutainer® tubes (Becton-Dickinson and Company, BD, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) without anticoagulant (for serum) or EDAT-K2 as anticoagulant (for plasma and erythrocytes), and were stored in darkness, in ice-containing receptacles. Both plasma and serum were separated by centrifugation at $1500 \times g$ for 15 min, within 1 h after extraction. Aliquots of supernatant (0.5 – 1 ml) were immediately frozen to -80°C until analysis. The study was carried out in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration and was approved by the hospital Ethical Committee.

Tab. 1. Overview of patient characteristics. Values are given as the mean \pm SD

	Patients
Gender (male/female)	5/17
Age (years)	29–58
Mean EDSS	4.8 \pm 1.69
Disease duration (years)	8.18 \pm 7.08

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of natalizumab infusion and blood extraction

Biochemical parameters

Carbonylated protein levels were measured from plasma using the method developed by Levine et al. [17, 18]. Quantitative measurement of the oxidative DNA adduct 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) was measured from plasma using a 8-OHdG Check-437-0122 assay kit purchased from JaICA (Japan Institute for the Control of Aging, Fukuroi City, Shizuoka, Japan) [30]. Reduced glutathione (GSH) levels were measured from erythrocytes using the Bioxytech GSH-400 kit (Oxis International, Portland, OR, USA). Glutathione peroxidase (GPx; EC 1.11.1.12) and superoxide dismutase (SOD; EC 1.15.1.1) activity were evaluated from erythrocytes by the Flohé and Gunzler method [7] and by a colorimetric assay kit purchased from BioVision (Mountain View, CA, USA), respectively. Total antioxidant capacity (PAO, KPA-050) was assayed from plasma using a kit purchased from JaICA [18]. Myeloperoxidase (MPO) levels were measured from plasma using ELISA kits purchased from Hycult Biotechnology B.V. (Uden, The Netherlands; e.g., MPO-human, HK210).

The antioxidant gap (GAP) was calculated using the following equation: $GAP = \text{total antioxidant capacity} - ([\text{Albumin} \times \text{TEAC}] + [\text{uric acid} \times \text{TEAC}])$ (TEAC = Trolox equivalents) [2, 19, 37]. This indicator consists in measuring plasma antioxidant activity of ascorbic acid, α -tocopherol, bilirubin, transferrin and other minority antioxidant compounds, excluding albumin, uric acid and Trolox equivalent [2, 37]. Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. designed an integral method for analyzing oxidative damage that includes different oxidative stress and antioxidant system parameters. These data may produce four possible scenarios: (i) no oxidative stress, (ii) antioxidant enzyme defi-

ciency (AEDN), (iii) antioxidant extracellular deficiency (AEXD), and (iv) antioxidant system global deficiency (ASGD) [37] (Tab. 3).

Immunological parameters

Quantitative measurement of serum vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 (sVCAM-1) and serum intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (sICAM-1) levels was performed using the Milliplex® MAP Kit, Human CVVD Panel 1 96-Well Plate Assay, (Millipore Corporation, Billerica, MA, USA).

Nrf2 evaluation

Extraction of nuclear and cytoplasmic proteins and western blot were performed as previously described [12]. The protein concentration was estimated using the Bradford's method [4].

Electrophoretic separation was carried out with 80 μg of protein of cytoplasmic and nuclear fractions. After separation in sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis gels (12% polyacrylamide), proteins were transferred to nitrocellulose membranes (Amersham Bioscience) by using a semi-dry transfer, following standard protocols. The membranes were washed and blocked with skimmed milk and incubated overnight at 4°C with primary antibody (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) against Nrf2 (anti-rabbit, 1 : 500), actin (anti-mouse, 1 : 300,000) as cytoplasmic control, and TFIIB (anti-rabbit, 1 : 500) as nuclear control. After incubation with primary antibodies, the membranes were incubated with secondary antibody [anti-rabbit IgG or anti-mouse IgG conjugated to HRP (Santa Cruz Biotechnology)]. The protein detection in the membranes was carried out with the chemilumi-

Tab. 2. Oxidative stress biomarker levels in the blood of patients with RR-MS. Data represent the means \pm SD. 8-OHdG: 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine; tG: total glutathione; GSH: reduced glutathione; PAO: total antioxidant capacity; GAP: antioxidant gap; GPx: glutathione peroxidase; SOD: superoxide dismutase; MPO: myeloperoxidase. Baseline: Patients with MS previous treatment; and MS-14: after 56 weeks (approx. 14 months, before the 14th infusion) of treatment with natalizumab

	Baseline Mean (SD)	MS-14 Mean (SD)	Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test (significance 2-tails)
Carbonylated proteins (nM)	0.8 (0.4)	0.6 (0.4) ^a	Z: -2.914; 95% Confidence interval in the means between: 0.0001-0.117
8-OHdG (ng/ml)	70.2 (38.6)	61.7 (27.7) ^a	Z: -3.600; 95% Confidence interval in the means between: 0.0002- 0.117
MPO (ng/ml)	274.0 (119.9)	153.2 (125.2) ^c	Z: -2.346; 95% Confidence interval in the means between: 0.007-0.117
MPO/neutrophil granulocytes	64.1 (65.6)	40.7 (32.1) ^b	Z: -2.772; 95% Confidence interval in the means between: 0.009- 0.117
tG (μ M/gHb)	78.5 (41.4)	79.2 (44.5)	ns
GSH (μ M/g Hb)	72.3 (37.3)	63.7 (39.5)	ns
GPx (U/ml/gHb)	0.1 (0.1)	0.1 (0.1)	ns
SOD (U/ml/gHb)	2.1 (0.8)	1.4 (1.3)	ns
PAO (mM)	0.2 (0.1)	0.2 (0.1)	ns
GAP (μ M)	1009.1 (446.3)	910.8 (669.0)	ns

^a p < 0.001 vs. baseline; ^b p < 0.01 vs. baseline; ^c p < 0.05 vs. baseline; ns = non significant

nescence kit Luminol Reagent Detection System (Santa Cruz Biotechnology). Next, the films were scanned in a GS-800 calibrated densitometer and were identified in the autoradiography by their position relative to molecular weight markers: 57 kDa for Nrf2, 40 kDa for actin and 34 kDa for TFIIB. Then, the signal band corresponding to the proteins were quantified by using the Quantity One 4,6,5 software (Bio-Rad Inc.). The results were calculated in terms of integrated optical density (IOD) and expressed in arbitrary units (AU).

Statistical analysis

Statistical evaluation was carried out using the SPSS17.0[®] statistical software package (SPSS Iberica, Madrid, Spain) for Windows. Inter-group statistical significance was measured by the Wilcoxon-matched pairs test to analyze nonparametric data; p < 0.05 was considered significant. Data are expressed as the means \pm SD.

Results

Serum VCAM-1 levels were significantly lower after 14 weeks' natalizumab treatment than at baseline (p < 0.001), whereas no significant changes were recorded in serum ICAM-1 levels (data not shown).

Changes in oxidative stress biomarkers in RR-MS patients treated with natalizumab versus baseline

RR-MS patients treated with natalizumab displayed a reduction in oxidative damage, characterized by a marked decline in carbonylated protein levels and DNA oxidation in plasma. No significant changes were observed in total glutathione levels, GSH, SOD and GPx activity, total antioxidant capacity or GAP (Tab. 2).

Natalizumab additionally prompted a significant reduction in MPO content and in the MPO/neutrophil granulocytes ratio (p < 0.05 and p < 0.01, respectively).

On the other hand, the interpretation of oxidative damage biomarkers based on normal cut-off points showed a reduction in total antioxidant capacity, antioxidant Gap levels and an increase in SOD/GPx ratio, carbonylated proteins and 8-OHdG levels in patient with RR-MS (Tab. 3B). After 14 months of treatment, the SOD/GPx ratio suffered changes characterized by a reduction in its value (Tab. 3B).

Changes in Nrf2 transcription factor levels

Analysis showed that natalizumab treatment had a substantial effect on Nrf2 expression and translocation (Figs. 2 and 3), not only by increasing nuclear

Tab. 3. Present an integral method for analyzing oxidative damage.

A) Oxidative stress biomarkers in control subjects obtained in 90 percentile of our population of healthy subjects, and interpretation of oxidative stress markers based on normal cut-off points according to our studied population of healthy subjects (n = 15) [31]

A) Oxidative status	SOD/GPx	Total antioxidant capacity (mM)	Antioxidant gap (μmol/l)	Carbonylated protein (nM)	8-OHdG (ng/ml)
Without oxidative stress	≤ 16.4	≥ 0.9	≥ 1013	≤ 0.6	≤ 66
Oxidative stress with AEDN	≤ 16.4	≥ 0.9	≥ 1013	≥ 0.6	≥ 66
Oxidative stress with AEXD	≤ 16.4	≥ 0.9	≤ 1013	≥ 0.6	≥ 66
Oxidative stress with ASGD	≤ 16.4	≥ 0.9	≤ 1013	≥ 0.6	≥ 66

B) Interpretation of oxidative stress markers in our MS patients

B) Groups	SOD/GPx	Total antioxidant capacity (mM)	Antioxidant gap (μmol/l)	Carbonylated protein (nM)	8-OHdG (ng/ml)
Baseline	≥ 16.4	≤ 0.9	≤ 1013	≥ 0.6	≥ 66
MS-14	≤ 16.4	≤ 0.9	≤ 1013	= 0.6	≤ 66

SOD/GPx was analyzed in erythrocytes and the rest of parameters in plasma. AEDN: antioxidant enzymatic deficiency; AEXD: antioxidant extracellular deficiency; ASGD: antioxidant system global deficiency. These data supported the hypothesis of a reduction of ASGD in MS patients before treatment with natalizumab (baseline). Whereas MS-14 group show an important drop in PAO and GAP without increases in PC and 8-OHdG markers, indicating the presence of AEXD, situation that indicates the recovery, at least in part, of intracellular antioxidant systems

concentrations in the PBMCs of patients with RR-MS compared with baseline levels but also by inducing a highly-significant increase in cytoplasmic concentrations. Moreover, natalizumab treatment prompted a significant increase in Nrf2 levels in both cytoplasm and nucleus.

Fig. 2. Levels of Nrf2 protein in nuclear and cytoplasmic fraction of PBMCs of patients with RR-MS. Bars represent the mean values ± SD. Samples displayed changes in both cytoplasmic and nuclear Nrf2 levels in Wilcoxon signed ranks test: i) Cytoplasm: Z: -1.826; 95% confidence interval in the means between: 0.0001-0.451); p < 0.001; and ii) Nucleus: Z: -1.826; 95% confidence interval in the means between: 0.0002-0.541); p < 0.001

Discussion

This study sought to examine the impact of natalizumab on oxidative-stress biomarker levels in the patients. The most striking finding was that natalizumab therapy reduced peripheral-blood oxidative damage, by prompting a reduction in carbonylated proteins and 8-OHdG, as well as in MPO levels and MPO/neutrophil granulocytes ratio. It also triggered nuclear translocation of Nrf2 in PBMCs. These changes were accompanied by a significant reduction in sVCAM-1 levels induced by natalizumab-treated MS patients, while there were no significant changes in sICAM-1 levels after 14 months' treatment. These findings shed some light on the mechanisms involved in the protective effect of natalizumab.

Previously-published data [32] also showed that patients presented a range of oxidative damage prior to natalizumab therapy, displaying what has been termed a global antioxidant system deficiency (GASD: extra- and intracellular). Interestingly, however, after 14 months' natalizumab therapy, these patients presented only extracellular antioxidant deficiency (EXAD), suggesting at least a degree of recovery of cellular antioxidant systems. This could, in itself, be of great im-

Fig. 3. Nrf2 protein measured by western blot in nuclear and cytoplasmic fractions of PBMC from RR-MS patient number 19. Baseline: Patients with MS previous treatment vs. MS-14: after 14 months' treatment with natalizumab. 19-Cb: Measurements in PBMC cytoplasm at baseline; 19-Nb: Measurements in PBMC nuclei at baseline; 19-CEM-14: Measurements in PBMC cytoplasm after 14 months' treatment; 19-NEM-14: Measurements in PBMC nuclei after 14 months' treatment; LC: Loading control. Actin and TFIIIB represent the cytoplasm and nuclear control, respectively

portance, in that it might account for the decline observed in oxidative damage biomarkers (carbonylated proteins and 8-OHdG) in natalizumab-treated patients. A recent study has reported that natalizumab reduced carbonylated proteins in the blood of patients with RR-MS [33], a finding borne out by the present results. The data obtained here also agree with findings observed by other authors, who have established a link between MS and oxidative stress, reporting endogenous antioxidant system impairment and increased oxidative/nitrative damage in MS patients, due to enhanced production of ROS/RNS by activated macrophages and microglia [13, 24, 32]. Supporting this idea, a number of published studies report that oxidative damage is more marked in MS patients than in healthy controls [13, 23, 24, 32]. Taken together, their findings confirm the link between oxidative injury and inflammation in multiple sclerosis. Blood oxidative-stress biomarkers have also been found to increase during relapses [31].

Here, natalizumab therapy over 14 months was found to exert a protective effect characterized by a reduction in oxidative stress biomarker levels compared to baseline values. This finding is indirectly borne out by research demonstrating that natalizumab reduces and/or blocks the synthesis of several inflammatory mediators, and that inflammatory systems exert their effect, in part, through the action of pro-oxidant enzymes [13, 24]. In the present study, moreover, natalizumab reduced levels of MPO, a pro-oxidant enzyme whose activity induces an increase in oxidative stress. This suggests that the pro-

TECTIVE effects of natalizumab involve other routes or mechanisms of action, such as binding to integrin expressed on the surface of activated T cells.

The enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant systems through which the body counters ROS/RNS production are controlled by a sophisticated mechanism regulated by transcription factor Nrf2 (nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2) [29, 34]. Nrf2-mediated biosynthesis and release regulates the expression of so-called "vitagenes" encoding various antioxidant proteins [15, 29].

The reduction in oxidative damage following natalizumab therapy may have been induced by a nuclear response prompted in part by nuclear translocation of the transcription factor Nrf2. This scenario is supported by the finding that natalizumab therapy was associated with increased cytoplasmic and nuclear Nrf2 compared to baseline levels. Additionally, the present results would appear to indicate that natalizumab not only increases Nrf2 translocation but also enhances Nrf2 expression.

In a recent study, Millionig et al. reported a significant drop in sVCAM-1 levels in natalizumab-treated MS patients within 4 weeks of treatment; by contrast, MS patients treated with interferon- β displayed higher sVCAM levels [21]. The authors suggested that natalizumab thus has a dual mechanism of action: it reduces transmigration not only by blocking VLA-4 but also by down-regulating sVCAM-1. However, the mechanism by which natalizumab down-regulates sVCAM-1 remains unclear.

Recent research has shown that Nrf2 activity inhibits VCAM-1 expression, protecting endothelial cells

from oxidant injury and inhibiting inflammatory gene expression [1, 5]. This finding is supported by the results of the present study, which revealed an increase in Nrf2 levels as well as nuclear translocation of Nrf2 in association with a fall in sVCAM-1 levels.

By prompting a decline in sVCAM-1 levels and an increase in Nrf2, natalizumab treatment appears to improve the oxidative environment and favor the integrity of the blood brain barrier, thus hindering activated immune cell transmigration.

This effect on sVCAM levels – given the well-documented relationship between ROS, NF- κ B and adhesion molecules – suggests that another possible mechanism through which natalizumab exerts its protective effect is the expression and/or translocation of NF- κ B, a phenomenon reported by a number of authors [8, 14, 22, 28, 36].

Finally, attention is drawn to two weaknesses and constraints in this study: i) lack of measurement of Nrf2-dependent gene expression; and ii) lack of measurement of NF- κ B levels. Although the number of patients studied may appear small, it should be remembered that natalizumab therapy is governed by very restrictive guidelines, and thus the available study population is necessarily limited.

In summary, this work provides evidence for the view that: i) the protective effects of natalizumab in MS patients involve a reduction in oxidative stress and MPO levels; ii) natalizumab acts to enhance levels and nuclear translocation of the transcription factor Nrf2; and iii) these changes may be additional to, or associated with, the inflammatory blockade, suggesting a link between oxidative stress and inflammation.

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